

STUDY OF TEACHERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS YOGA EDUCATION

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Abstract

The word Yoga is derived from the root word 'Yuj', which generally means 'to join'. In spiritual language, Yoga means the merging of a person's soul with God in such a way that there is no separation from it again and that soul itself becomes God. In other words, Yoga means 'to meet' like the soul meeting in God. The meeting of Sun and Moon from which joyful (sukha) energy flows is the cause of salvation. Just as when hydrogen and oxygen mix, a third substance, water is formed, when both of them mix, a new substance is created. Similarly, by the union of mind and life, by the union of Sun and Moon, a new thing is born. Similarly, by doing yoga, something new is born in man. Its name is yoga. Yoga is a complete science, a complete way of life, a complete medical practice and a complete spiritual discipline. The present research has studied the attitude of teachers towards yoga education. The results were obtained by statistical calculation by administering tests to measure attitude towards yoga education on teachers and educationists of rural and urban areas of Patna district. From which it has been found that rural teachers are more inclined towards yoga education than urban teachers. Whereas urban teachers pay more attention to yoga than rural teachers. Therefore, if the attitude of teachers towards yoga education is positive, then undoubtedly healthy, skilled, strong and virtuous citizens will be prepared in India.

Keywords: Yoga, Teacher, Teacher's attitude.

Introduction

In the modern era, human life has become more struggling after the abundance of material comforts. Life is full of complications. Yoga is a functional discipline through which man develops his physical, mental, intellectual, emotional and spiritual at all levels and consequently can meet all the challenges born at the exciting pace of modern technological

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age. It is the beauty of the yogic processes that all the potentialities take definite shape in unison with man's spiritual progress, which helps man to become aware of this whole universe full of inherent powers and possibilities through his self-awakening, to transform his own life through the knowledge of the eternal and infinite, and to attain inner harmony and peace. Today, yoga has become not just a spiritual practice but an art of living where a person is trying to live a peaceful and stress-free life by centering the mind by taking time out of his running life. New researches in this field have given a new form of life by motivating people towards natural and real life in a revolutionary way and the person is getting rid of serious and incurable diseases like cancer, AIDS and Hepatitis-B etc. through yoga. Due to the atmosphere of insecurity, fear, unrest in the society, today the child fails to perform his actions and behavior independently in that environment and achieve the goal, due to which the glands of mental and emotional stress get dwelled in him and the child keeps struggling with them, which blocks the path of his development.

Today, the Education Department, realizing the usefulness of yoga, has started yoga education in all schools from primary and upper primary level to high school level. With the gradual development of yoga education, their timely and appropriate training is very important. The benefits of teachers' training will reach the students and develop knowledge in them. At present, new schemes are also being implemented by the government on the educational importance and need of yoga. Therefore, it becomes necessary to get information about the attitude of teachers towards yoga education.

Objectives of the research

The objectives of the research are as follows:

1. To make a comparative study of the attitude of urban and rural male teachers towards yoga education.
2. To make a comparative study of the attitude of urban and rural women teachers towards yoga education.
3. To make a comparative study of the attitude of male and female teachers towards yoga education.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses of the research presented are as follows:

1. There is a significant difference in the attitude of urban and rural teachers towards yoga education.

2. There is a significant difference in the attitude of urban and rural teachers towards yoga education.

3. There is a significant difference in the attitude of male teachers and female teachers towards yoga education.

Delimitations

The present research has been delimited as follows:

1. Research has been delimited to Patna district.
2. Research has been delimited to 25 teachers of Fatuha block of Patna district for rural area.
3. In the urban area, it is delimited to 25 teachers from the Patna town.

Research Process

Research Method: Survey method has been selected for the present study.

Design: 50 teachers (25 female, 25 male teachers) have been selected from Fatuha block for rural area and Patna town for urban area of Patna district. Sample is selected by purposive sampling method.

Tools: Self-made research tool has been used by the researcher.

Test for Measurement of Attitude: This instrument was administered to assess the attitude of teachers towards yoga. This self-made scale consists of 55 statements and a total of 110 marks have been determined. It was scheduled to administer 30 minutes.

Variables: The classification of variables in the research presented is as follows:

1. Independent Variables - Teachers
2. Dependent Variables- Attitude towards Yoga Education

Statistical Analysis: In the research presented, the mean for statistical analysis, standard deviation, the consistency of the difference of the mean were calculated.

Hypothesis No. 01

“There is a significant difference in the attitude of urban and rural teachers towards yoga education”.

Table No. 01

S. No.	Description	Mean of attitude towards yoga education	SD	Value of CR	df	Significance
1	Urban Teacher	90.4	9.1	3.08	48	The obtained CR value is higher than the value at the 1% confidence level is 2.68. So there is a Significant difference.
2	Rural Teacher	97.4	6.8			

The value obtained from the calculation of the data is greater than the degree of freedom 48 and the CR value obtained from the table at the 1% confidence level is 2.68. Hence, hypothesis No. 01 is accepted. Rural teachers were found to be more inclined towards yoga education than urban teachers.

Hypothesis- 02

"There is a significant difference in the attitude of urban and rural teachers towards yoga education".

Table No. 02

S. No.	Description	Mean of attitude towards yoga education	SD	Value of CR	df	Significance
1	Urban Teacher	101.56	9.1	3.06	48	The obtained CR value is higher than the value at the 1% confidence level is 2.68. So there is a Significant difference.
2	Rural Teacher	93.7	5.8			

The value obtained from the calculation of the data is 3.6, which is higher than the tabular value obtained at df 48 and at the 1% confidence level is 2.68. Hence, hypothesis no. 02 is accepted. The attitude of urban teachers towards yoga education was found to be more than that of rural teachers.

Hypothesis No. 03

"There will be a significant difference in the attitude of male teachers and female teachers towards yoga education".

Table No. 03

S. No.	Description	Mean of attitude towards yoga education	SD	Value of CR	df	Significance
1	Male Teacher	93.9	8.75	4.43	98	The obtained CR value is higher than the value at the 1% confidence level is 2.68. So there is a Significant difference.
2	Female Teacher	101.18	7.63			

The value of CR obtained from calculating the data is 4.43 which is greater than the value 2.68 required for significance at the 1 percent confidence level. Hence, hypothesis No. 03 was accepted. Women teachers were found to be more inclined towards yoga education.

Conclusion: The conclusions obtained from the present research are as follows-

1. Rural teachers are more inclined towards yoga education than urban teachers. The reason for this is that life in the city is full of hectic days, where teachers are unable to find time to fulfill their desires. Therefore, even if they want, they do not devote as much time to yoga education as rural teachers. Yoga was propagated by workers going from village to village. Therefore, the attitude of rural teachers towards yoga is more than that of urban teachers.
2. Urban teachers pay more attention to yoga than rural teachers. The reason for this is that urban teachers are more conscious of improving their health and personality.
3. Female teachers are more inclined towards yoga than male teachers.

Suggestions: Based on the research findings, the following suggestions are presented-

1. Teachers should encourage students of all classes to study yoga and increase their self-confidence, which can increase their mental ability and adjustment capacity.
2. To increase the concentration of the students, the teacher should make them a habit of pronouncing Om (ॐ) daily.

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